

Spectrophotometric Determination of Iron as Iron(II) Thiocyanate Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide

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A spectrophotometric method of determination of iron is described. The red complex formed between iron(II), thiocyanate and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide is extractable into benzene. Addition of borate enhances the colour intensity. Absorbance, measured at 475 nm, shows a linear response upto 1.5 ppm of iron. Molar absorptivity of the complex and Sandell's sensitivity are determined and interferences studied. Iron has been determined in synthetic mixtures.

THIOCYANATE is extensively used for the colourimetric determination of iron, even though other reagents may give better results. The metal can be determined spectrophotometrically by using chrome azurol S and hexadecyltrimethylammonium chloride¹.

Nagahiro *et al.*² determined iron(II) by extraction of its ion-association complex with 5,6-diphenyl-3-(4-phenyl-2-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazine and tetraphenyl borate into molten naphthalene. Another highly sensitive and selective method for spectrophotometric determination³ of iron(II) involves the use of bromopyrogallol red and pyrogallol red in presence of tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide. Bayan⁴ developed a method to determine trace amounts of iron(III) using benzyltriethylammonium chloride and thiocyanate in presence of ethyl methyl ketone. The complex is extractable into 1,2-dichloroethane. Numerous other reagents are found reported for spectrophotometric determination of iron. Here we present a highly sensitive method involving application of ammonium thiocyanate and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide(CTA).

In our present investigation it has been found that the above reagents form red complex with iron(II) as well as iron(III). Addition of small amounts of sodium tetraborate enhances the colour of the solution initially containing iron as iron(II). To a solution containing iron as iron(III), addition of borate does not bring about any change in color intensity. Extraction into benzene of the ion-pair formed between the thiocyanate complex of iron(II) and the quarternary ammonium ion from cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTA) and measurement of absorbance of the organic extract, forms the basis of the method.

Experimental

Spectral measurements were made on a Shimadzu PR1 spectrophotometer, equipped with matched quartz cells of 10 mm optical path-length. An

ECL 5651 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

All chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade. A stock solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate was prepared by dissolving it in distilled water and acidified with HCl (2-3 drops) and then standardised⁵.

Solutions of ammonium thiocyanate (0.2 M), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTA) (0.1 M) and sodium tetraborate (0.025 M) were prepared in distilled water. KCl-HCl buffer was used to adjust pH of the aqueous solution.

Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from chlorides, nitrates or sulphates (in case of cations) and from sodium, potassium or ammonium salts (in case of anions) of the species concerned, to study interferences.

Procedure : To an aliquot of standard solution or sample containing upto 15 μg of iron(II), were added 0.2 M ammonium thiocyanate (0.5 ml), 0.1 M cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (0.1 ml) and 0.025 M sodium tetraborate solution (0.5 ml). KCl-HCl buffer (pH 1.0; 5 ml) and water as necessary were added to the above solution to give a total volume of 10 ml. The resulting mixture was equilibrated with benzene (10 ml) for 30 s. After phase separation, organic layer was poured over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove any retained water. The absorbance of the organic extract was measured against a blank at 475 nm and the metal concentration computed from a calibration curve. To test the interference, the respective foreign ion was added to the aqueous solution before addition of the reagents.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The iron complex (in benzene) exhibits absorption maxima at 475 nm. The reagent blank itself, shows insignificant absorbance in this wavelength region. The pattern

of the absorption spectrum of the complex, extracted throughout the entire range, i.e. from 4 M HCl medium to pH 1.0, remains unchanged. This indicates the presence of a single variety of the complex species in the system.

Spectral curves of benzene extracts obtained by applying the procedure to the solutions initially containing iron as iron(II) were identical in nature to those from iron(III) solutions.

Beer's law and reagent concentrations: The absorbance of the red complex in benzene shows a linear response upto 1.5 ppm of iron. The molar absorptivity of the complex, based on iron content, and the Sandell's sensitivity were calculated at 475 nm (Table 1).

With the variation of the reagent concentrations, it was found that 0.5 ml of 0.2 M ammonium thiocyanate along with 0.1 ml of 0.1 M cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and 0.5 ml of 0.025 M borate were sufficient to extract 9 µg of iron in a single operation. Increased concentration of the reagents, however, did not bring about any significant change in the λ_{\max} value. Addition of borate raised the intensity of the colour when iron was present initially as iron(II). To a solution containing iron as iron(III), addition of borate had no effect.

Addition of reagents: Addition of reagents is important in the procedure. One must follow the sequence of adding the reagents as: thiocyanate, CTA, borate and buffer. No colour development was noted when borate was added before thiocyanate.

Effect of acidity: Effect of acidity on the system was examined in terms of absorbance of the complex in the organic phase. Maximum absorbance was obtained when the extractions were carried out from 4 M HCl medium to pH 1.0. In each case, the remaining aqueous phase, after a single operation, was clear and colourless. Furthermore, the aqueous phase, as tested by an independent method, was void of iron. Complete and quantitative extraction of iron occurred in the entire range. At higher acid concentrations, difficulty arises in separating the organic layer due to the formation of some emulsion. Beyond pH 1.0, iron showed no colour reaction with the reagents in the aqueous phase. The reagent blank absorbs minimum at pH 1.0, hence extractions were carried out at pH 1.0.

Effects of solvents and stability: Amongst the several solvents benzene, ethyl acetate, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and butanol, and benzene were found to be suitable solvents for extraction of the iron complex (Table 1). The rapid development of the maximum absorbance and constancy of the absorbance with time indicate that time is not a critical factor in the determination. Spectral curves of the iron complex extracted into other water-immiscible liquids are identical in nature.

Interference: To test the effects of diverse ions on the extraction behaviour, iron(II) was extracted

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SOLVENTS*

Solvent	λ_{\max} nm	Molar absorptivity $\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-1}$
Benzene	475	3.59	0.001 5
Ethyl acetate	480	2.99	0.001 8
Chloroform	470	2.66	0.002 1
Carbon tetrachloride	NE	NE	NE
Butanol	NE	NE	NE

*NE = Complex not extractable.

and determined according to the recommended procedure in presence of the diverse ions. Extraction pH was set at 1.0, unless otherwise mentioned. An ion was considered to interfere if the recovery of iron differed by more than $\pm 3\%$ from the actual amount taken. Iron(II) (9 µg) could be determined without interference in presence of 500-fold excess of Al^{III} , Ba^{II} , Be^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ce^{III} , Cd^{II} , Cr^{III} , La^{III} , Pb^{II} , Mg^{II} , Ni^{II} , Rh^{III} , Bi^{III} , Ti^{I} , Th^{IV} , U^{VI} , Zr^{IV} and Ag^{I} ; 250-fold excess of Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Mo^{VI} ; and 50-fold excess of Pt^{IV} . Upto 50-fold excess of V^{V} could be tolerated provided the extraction be carried out from 3 M HCl medium. In presence of Cu^{II} , the benzene extract became hazy and the absorbance of the organic layer could not be measured, and attempts to remove this interference failed. Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} and Sn^{II} must be absent, as iron(II) showed no colour reaction with the reagents in presence of them. Presence of Pd^{II} resulted low recovery of iron.

Among the anions tested, the presence of more than 500-fold excess of citrate, tartrate, acetate, phthalate, phosphate, nitrate had no effect. Extraction should be carried out from 3 M HCl medium to avoid the interference due to EDTA, fluoride and oxalate. The system, however, was found to be susceptible in presence of iodide, nitrite and ascorbate. In 3 M HCl medium 100-fold excess of thiourea could be tolerated.

Precision and accuracy: The proposed method was tested by analysing solutions containing a known amount of iron(II). The experimental results for the determination of 3–12 µg of iron(II) are shown in Table 2. The method is fairly precise and reproducible, requiring 10–15 min for each run.

TABLE 2—REPRODUCIBILITY OF IRON RECOVERY

Fe^{II} taken μg	Fe^{II} found μg			Mean μg	Std. Dev. %
3.0	3.1	3.0	2.9	2.96	0.10
	2.8	3.0	3.0		
6.0	6.2	6.0	5.9	5.95	0.15
	6.0	5.8	5.8		
9.0	9.0	9.2	8.9	9.05	0.12
	9.2	9.0	9.0		
12.0	11.8	12.0	12.2	12.00	0.17
	12.2	12.0	11.8		

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF IRON (9 µg) IN VARIOUS MIXTURES WITH 200 µg OF EACH ION ADDED

Sl. no.	Ions added	Fe found µg
1.	CoII, NiII, MnII	9.1, 9.1, 9.2
2.	NiII, MnII, CrIII	9.0, 9.2, 9.0
3.	MnII, CrIII, BiIII	9.3, 9.1, 9.0
4.	CrIII, BiIII, PbII	8.9, 9.1, 9.1
5.	AlIII, CdII, ThIV	9.0, 9.1, 9.1

The method has been tested on a number of synthetic mixtures and the results are shown in Table 3.

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